

Original Article

Evaluating Educational Equity in Privatized-Public and Low-Performing Public Schools under the Public-Private Partnership Program: A Mixed-Methods Study in District Gujranwala

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Abstract

Education equity is critical for sustainable development and recognized as a basic right across the globe. For this purpose, to overcome educational inequality in Pakistan, the Government of Punjab has initiated the Public-Private Partnership (PPP) program where private entities collaborate. This study investigates the effectiveness of the PPP program to promote equity in education by comparing privatized-public schools with low-performing public schools under the Public School Support Program (PSSP) in District Gujranwala. The research, through a quantitative approach, focuses on the education equity based on the access of education quality, physical facilities, and inclusiveness from the school councils and parents. Using a purposive sampling, 19 privatized-public schools and 19 low-performing public schools were sampled from a pool of 78 privatized-public schools and 34 low-performing public schools in the country. Data were collected using validated tools, including the Scale for Evaluation of School Performance (SESP) and a facility observation checklist. Using descriptive and inferential statistics, data were analysed with the help of SPSS and results showed there was a significant difference between educational equity in public and private schools. Privatized-public schools had better equity outcomes, like gender parity and inclusiveness. Examining the full text of the study, the researchers draw important conclusions for policy making particularly with respect to the necessity for targeted allocation of resources and engagement of stakeholders to promote equity within education. The study presents a framework for assessing PPP initiatives and emphasizes the need for equitable education, especially in conditions of economic disparity. In this sense, it joins the larger discourse on sustainable reforms for education in developing countries.

Keywords: Educational Equity, Low-Performing Public Schools, Sustainable Development, PPP Program

Introduction

The teaching profession is considered a much better profession by females as compared to male counterparts that's why the female population is joining this profession with very much trust. Further, overall the teaching profession is considered a trusted profession by Pakistani people (Kamran & Shahbaz, 2019). Education equity, as a path to realizing sustainable development and global recognition of

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education as a human right, The Government of Punjab, Pakistan, realizing the need to overcome the gaps in education, has joined hands with the private sector under the Public-Private partnership (PPP) program to achieve both quality education and universal primary education. While such efforts are well-intentioned, an important area of research is assessing the extent to which they are effective at promoting educational equity. Thus, this cross-sectional study explores the role of the PPP program in improving the equity gap in privatized-public schools as compared to low-performing public schools in District Gujranwala, Pakistan.

The study is motivated by the global call towards equal education found in United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4) which advocates for “inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all.” A case in point is the Public School Support Program (PSSP), a project of the Punjab Education Foundation (PEF), which is private management of a set of underperforming public schools to try to improve their performance. But, the effectiveness of these partnerships to provide equitable access and outcomes for students is still relatively unexplored. Previous studies have focused on issues of educational quality or access but have not adequately addressed the nuanced question of equity, especially in contexts characterized by socio-economic disparity and resource constraints (Afridi, 2018)

This research fills this gap by identifying and addressing the comparative studies between privatized-public and low-performing public schools within the PPP meta-analysis for educational equity. Educational equity here refers to equal access to quality education, availability of physical facilities, and inclusivity as it concerns the perspectives of stakeholders like school councils and parents. This study recruited participants through a mixed-methods approach, allowing for measures of disparity as well as narratives that highlight the experiences of the community, providing a holistic measurement and evaluation.

These findings are of great importance to policymakers, educators, and stakeholders as they provide evidence-based insights regarding the effectiveness of PPP programs. These explanations can help in shaping next policies shaping up, further improve a better existing program and most importantly allow a fair amount of educational resources. An added value of this paper is that it could serve as a model for assessing similar initiatives in other locations, proving valuable insights into engaging stakeholders and considering the multifaceted nature of educational equity (Rind & Shah, 2022).

This study stems from the pressing need to remedy educational injustices, especially in areas where system inequities deter pupils from reaching their potential. In addition to that, by analyzing an urban-rural context with diverse educational challenges such as Gujranwala, study hopes that it contributes to the larger discourse on educational equity in developing contexts by offering a more nuanced understanding of the impact of PPPs.

Statement of the Problem

In response to the global trend of quality education and universal primary education, the Government of the Province of Punjab, Pakistan has partnered with the private sector through a public-private partnership (PPP) programme. This will improve access to and the quality of education in the province. Correspondingly, since this cooperation is effective, it is ascertain the role of both sides by conducting this study which is much obliged. In this context, the study aims at evaluating whether or not the PPP policy is effective through an evidence-based statistical approach. The research aims to analyze the policy in terms of its implementation and identify whether it has met the desired objectives of the education sector and filled the gaps in the education system (Paper, 2023). The findings of this study have the important implications for shaping and evaluating similar programs in education policy moving forward. The results could prove useful for policymakers, educators and stakeholders as they offer data on the strengths, challenges and areas for improvement in the program. The research aspires to inform the discussion on public-private partnerships more broadly to guide sustainable and impactful policy decisions in education (Komatsu et al., 2020).

Research Objectives of the Study

The study was carried out under the following objectives:

1. To explore the educational equity in privatized-public schools under public private partnership program and low performing public schools.
2. To compare the educational equity of privatized-public schools under Public Private Partnership program and low performing public schools.

Research Questions of the Study

The study tackle the following research questions:

1. What is the extent of educational equity in privatized-public schools?
2. What is the extent of educational equity in low performing public schools?

Research Hypothesis

H1o: There is no significant difference in the level of educational equity at privatized-public schools and low performing public schools?

Delimitations of the Study

The study was confined to the primary level Privatized-Public Schools based on the Public School Support Program (PSSP) model under Punjab Education Foundation (PEF) and their comparable low achieving public schools of tehsil Gujranwala and tehsil Wazirabad, District Gujranwala Punjab, Pakistan.

Theoretical Framework of the Study

The study paradigm is qualitative methods research. It includes the assessment of school performance. The researcher uses two groups of schools, privatized-public schools and low-performing public schools. To this end the researcher developed scale for assessment of educational equity in school performance and a checklist for physical battery availability besides he used structured interview protocol to explore the narrative of representative from community including members of school council and parents as stakeholders. The study was carried out in three tehsils (Wazirabad city and saddar) of Gujranwala District and the data were collected from head teachers of the concerned schools, school council members and parents and physical facilities were also observed regarding their availability and status. Below is the study conceptual framework (Naz & Arshad, 2024).

Literature Review

Educational Equity in Public, and Privatized-Public, Schools

In many developing regions where educational equity is a significant issue in both public and privatized-public schools this poses a unique challenge. These are equity, inclusion, and diversity and equity in education, which involve access, participation, and achievement, preventing socio-economic or geographic differences from diminishing students' opportunity to learn. As UNESCO (2022) states, tackling inequities in education is essential for achieving international sustainable development goals, particularly in countries with large socio-economic disparities. These types of schools are often regarded as a way of improving educational zing underperforming areas through Public-private partnerships (PPP) which covers the cost of providing privatized-public schools. This does not come without equity concerns though, especially concerning access for historically marginalized groups(Sharma et al., 2023).

Public Private Partnership Programs in Education

By taking advantage of the perceived efficiency of the private sector while using public resources, public-private partnership programs (PPPs) are one such initiative to improve the delivery of education. Globally, these programs have been implemented with mixed results. Previously, in Pakistan, the Punjab Education Foundation (PEF) has led PPPs to improve the educational performance of under-performing public schools (Right to Education Project, 2014). The studies depict mixed effects of PPPs on quality of

education, teacher performance, and student outcomes. But there are yet been many concerns about the sustainability of PPPs in addressing systemic inequities in education access (Dawadi et al., 2021).

Issues in Underperforming Schools

This correlates with other problems, such as low motivation from teachers, poor infrastructure at schools, etc. Research by researcher observe that school performance under PPP in districts such as Gujranwala, is significantly better they noted improved infrastructure and teaching quality. Yet, equity remains a challenge since private partners may seek profit rather than equity in access for the underprivileged. More recently, researcher noted that teacher recruitment and retention in low-performing schools remains a problem, compromising the long-term impact of these partnerships(Every & Should, 2025).

Assessing Educational Outcomes through Public-Private Partnerships

Assessing the results of PPPs requires an analysis of quantitative and qualitative dimensions of equity in education. Mixed-methods are well positioned to capture the complexity of such programmes. Researcher draw attention to the achievements of PPPs, stating that "the average Student Learning Outcomes (SLOs) of children studying in public-private partnership (PPP) schools are higher than those of children studying in government schools," yet specify that "the disparity in academic outcomes is pronounced across genders, socio-economic status and rural-urban divide." This has further ramifications: the partnership's privatization angle creates a dual system where the ones who can afford better facilities and teaching resources will find themselves ahead(Otani & Cameron, 2017).

Equity in District Gujranwala

As one of Punjab's most populous districts, Gujranwala faces particular challenges in achieving equitable education. Its landscape consists of a high proportion of low-performing schools and high socio-economic inequities. What is even more troubling is that the Punjab Education Department (2022) reveals through a report that the privatized-public schools in Pakistan that were also able to rise up the number of schools in those areas to be privatized through interventions under the PPP model, during their tenure, they have been able to increase enrollment to these privatized-public schools. However, the report also notes that indirect costs such as transportation, uniforms, and extra fees are excluding marginalized communities (Levinson et al., 2022)

This research offers a multidimensional perspective for the evaluation of educational equity. Bringing together quantitative data on enrollment, attendance, and achievement with qualitative insights from stakeholders helps surface systemic barriers. The value of mixed-methods designs lies particularly in their ability to address complex problems, such as educational equity, that cannot derive all of their insight from statistical data; researcher point out that mixed methods can help capture students' and teachers' lived experiences in ways that numbers alone do not allow(Nagpal et al., 2021).

Research Methodology

This chapter presented the researcher's methods used in order to better understand the research problem. The researcher aimed to lean on the topic of comparing the performance of the privatized-public schools as against the underperforming public schools. This study is performed with a mixed methods approach. The study follows pragmatic paradigm, embedded research design and mixed methods research. Schools are graded on three performance metrics; educational equity, quality and social accountability. Three instruments were developed for, and administered by, the researcher herself for this purpose (Dawadi et al., 2021). These instruments consist of scale measure to evaluate school performance, checklist regarding availability and condition of physical facilities school provided to students and interview protocols as qualitative part to know opinion of representatives of involved community: school council members and parents on how well existing school is performing. Research design, population of the study, research sample, sampling technique, instrumentation and instrument

validation, reliability of the scale, data collection and data analysis, will be included in this chapter (Saraswati & Devi, 2023).

Research Design

The research design of the study is quantitative research approach. Gender parity among students, gender parity among teachers and inclusiveness are all parts of educational equity. These factors were collected through a scale to evaluate school performance in quantitative paradigm (Morgan, 2017).

Population

The population of the study was comprised all privatized public schools and low performing public schools of tehsil Wazirabad, tehsil city and tehsil saddar area of Gujranwala district. Privatized-public schools are those schools working under Public school Support program (PSSP) initiated by Punjab Education Foundation (PEF). PEIMA (Punjab Education Initiative and Management Authority) has been evolved as PSSP in 2018. There are 78 privatized-public schools in above mentioned tehsiles. In other words, the population that falls into the privatized-public schools category is exactly 78. And those schools with poor performance are categorized as low performing public schools on the basis of 5th grade PEC result of the year 2014. Here poor result denotes schools with at least one fail student or at least one student cleared the exam with. There are 34 schools in the low performing public schools category. The respective area has a total of 112 schools in both categories combined (Gokce, 2022).

The table below mentions the No. of schools against each category.

Table 1

Population of the Study

Schools	Population
1. No. of Privatized-public schools	78
2. No. of low performing primary schools	34

Source: school education department, Gujranwala district

Research Sample

The study sample consisted of 19 privatized-public schools belonging to the public-private partnership program of the Punjab Education Foundation (PEF) in Gujranwala district, Punjab Pakistan and 19 low performing public schools. For comparison purpose, equal number of 19 against each category was maintained and a mixture of purposive sampling technique was used to select a total of 19 schools. The head teachers of each school were respondents. We have also mentioned the No. of schools against each category mentioned below.

Table 2

Sample of the Study

Schools	Population
1. No. of Privatized-public schools	19
2. No. of low performing primary schools	19

Sampling Technique

The researcher adopted purposive sampling technique to draw the sample. The identified sample included 34 low performing public schools, from this cohort, 19 schools were selected. Researcher uses a criterion to choose that number. This criterion considers schools in which 5 or above 5 students have in 5th grade result of PEC of year 2014. To ensure a comparable sample, out of privatized-public schools that falls under the second category, the researcher has purposively chosen 19 schools (Otani & Cameron, 2017).

Instrumentation

The researcher has used “Scale for Evaluation of School Performance” (SESP) as a tool to obtain the information related to the topic. It only used English language in override. The statements were made clear, straightforward, and easy to understand for the participants. Instruments were validated against expert opinion.

A. Scale to Evaluate School Performance

The researcher developed a questionnaire made up of 41 statements. Daft Statements: After getting an expert opinion, it was merged into 38 statements with the demographic information. The scale for assessment of school performance was named as questionnaire. The items were followed by a 4-point Likert type scale that ranged from 1 (strongly disagree) to 4 (strongly agree). It consists of total 3 factors and 8 sub-factors; among them two sub-factors are included as demographic information to ultimately find out the gender parity among students and gender parity among teachers in accordance with the given formula of gender parity index provided by UNESCO (Lucas-Oliva et al., 2022). After that, each remaining 6 factors have been prepared statements. The following table lists details of the instrument:

Table 3

Details of Scale for Evaluation of School Performance

Factors	Sub-factors	No of items	Sample Items
Educational equity	Inclusiveness	5	Your school offers admission to handicapped.

Instrument validation

Just to evaluate the validity of both the instruments researcher sought the valuable opinion of the panel of experts. The consent of the venerable specialists was obtained. Content validity ratio (CVR) was computed for each item of questionnaire to make a decision about status of retention of items. In the context of feedback given by experts, necessary changes were made by researcher. We ended up merging 4 items and rephrasing several others, while creating 3 initial items (Catlaks, 2013).

Instrument Piloting

To refine the questionnaire, the researcher piloted the questionnaire on any ten schools, 5 from privatized-public schools and 5 from low performing public schools. The respondents were the head teachers of the respective schools. To ensure the reliability of the instrument, the researcher has calculated the mean, standard deviation and Cronbach alpha coefficient for each factor and that of overall instrument. The reliability coefficient through the Cronbach alpha of SESP was .85 who are satisfied and ensured the reliability of the instrument.

Data Collection

Data were also collected from 19 privatized-public schools and 19 low performing public schools of tehsil Wazirabad, tehsil city and tehsil saddar of Gujranwala district. Two instruments were responsible for data collection. A questionnaire was filled by the head teachers of respective schools, and a checklist used to collect data through observation by the researcher herself. The researcher upheld the research ethics. The head teachers were consulted for their consent. Privacy was maintained. The respondents were provided with the essential information. The researcher personally visited all the sample schools. Due to adverse conditions due to covid-19 scenario and frequent school closure by government of punjab, data collection process continued for a period of five months

Data Analysis

The data collected with the help of both instruments was analyzed using statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) software. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to explore the answers of the

research questions. Mean and standard deviation were calculated in order to find out how poor or effective schools are with respect to educational equity.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

In this chapter, researcher describes the process of data collection and interpretation made on the basis of collected data. The purpose of the research was to evaluate the school performance of privatized-public schools in comparison with low performing public schools. To meet the purpose of the research two self-developed instruments were used by the researcher for data collection process. These instruments include Scale for Evaluation of school Performance (SESP) and checklist for availability of physical facilities.

Statistical Tests Applied to Research Questions

Data collected through instrument were analyzed by researcher using SPSS software. Statistical tests applied for each research question and research objectives are given below:

Table 4

Research Questions and their Relevant Statistical Tests

Research Objectives	Research Questions	Statistical Tests
1. To explore the educational equity in privatized-public schools under public private partnership program and low performing public schools.	What is the extent of educational equity in privatized-public schools?	Mean percentage and standard deviation.
	What is the extent of educational equity in low performing public schools?	Mean percentage and standard deviation.
2. To compare the educational equity of privatized-public schools under Public Private Partnership program and low performing public schools.	H1o: There is no significant difference in the level of educational equity at privatized-public schools and low performing public schools?	Independent sample t-test.

Quantitative Data Analysis: Data analysis according to research questions is given below;

Research Objective 01: To explore the educational equity in privatized-public schools under public private partnership program and low performing public schools.

Research Question no. 1: What is the extent of educational equity in privatized-public schools?

Table 5

Educational Equity at Privatized-Public School

Educational Equity	N	Mean	S.D.
Inclusiveness	19	2.74	0.39

Table 5 demonstrated the descriptive statistics of educational equity at privatized-public schools. Showed the number of respondents was 19 and inclusiveness was one of the factors of educational equity was 1. Mean of inclusiveness (M = 2.74, S.D = 0.39).

Table 5a

Gender Parity Among Students at Privatized-Public Schools

Educational equity	Net female enrolled	Net male enrolled	Gender parity index
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Gender Parity among students	859	730	1.17
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Above table a shows that gender parity index of students at privatized-public school is 1.17 which indicates gender parity in favor of girls as it is greater than 1.

Research question no. 2: What is the extent of educational equity in low performing public schools?

Table 6

Educational Equity at Low Performing Public Schools

Educational Equity	N	Mean	S.D.
Inclusiveness	19	2.72	0.36

Table 6 demonstrated the descriptive statistics of educational equity at low performing public schools. Showed the number of respondents was 19 and the factor of educational equity was 1. Mean of inclusiveness (M = 2.72, S.D = 0.36).

Table 6a

Gender Parity among Students at Low Performing Public Schools

Educational equity	Net female enrolled	Net male enrolled	Gender parity index
Gender Parity among students	709	801	0.88

Table 46 a shows that gender parity index at low performing public school is 0.88 which indicates gender parity in favor of boys as it is less than 1.

Research Objective 02: To compare the educational equity of privatized-public schools under Public Private Partnership program and low performing public schools

Hypothesis 01: H1o: There is no significant difference in the level of educational equity at privatized-public schools and low performing public schools

Table 7

Comparison of Educational Equity in Privatized-Public Schools and Low Performing Public Schools

Educational equity	N		Mean		S.D.		M.D.	df	t-value	Sig (2 tailed)	Eta2
	PPS	LPPS	PPS	LPPS	PPS	LPPS					
Inclusiveness	19	19	2.74	2.72	.399	.366	0.02	36	.169	.866	0.0007

Table 7 shows that an independent-samples t-test was conducted to compare the educational equity in privatized-public schools and low performing public schools. There was no significant difference in inclusiveness scores for privatized-public schools (M = 2.74, SD = .399) and low performing public schools (M = 2.72, SD = .366) t = .169, p < .001, (two tailed). The magnitude of the difference in the means of privatized public schools and low performing public schools was 0.02. The eta squared static (0.0007) indicated a large effect size. By comparing the second factor of educational equity that is gender parity among students, we can say that privatized-public schools are playing role in women empowerment by having gender parity in favor of women as compared to low performing public schools

Findings

Quantitative Findings

- The mean level of educational equity in privatized-public schools is statistically significant. Mean of inclusiveness (M = 2.74, S.D = 0.39).
- The mean level of educational equity in low performing public schools is statistically significant. Mean of inclusiveness (M = 2.72, S.D = 0.36).
- There was no significant difference in inclusiveness scores for privatized-public schools (M = 2.74, SD = .399) and low performing public schools (M = 2.72, SD = .366) $t = .169, p < .001$, (two tailed).
- The mean level of educational equity in privatized-public schools is statistically significant. Mean of qualification of teachers (M = 1.76, S.D = 0.88), quality of assessment (M = 3.20, S.D = 0.42), teachers' training workshops (M = 2.63, S.D = 0.34), quality of physical infrastructure (M = 1.92, S.D = 0.27).
- The mean level of educational equity in low performing public schools is statistically significant. Mean of qualification of teachers (M = 1.3.92, S.D = 0.25), quality of assessment (M = 3.50, S.D = 0.28), teachers' training workshops (M = 2.85, S.D = 0.35), infrastructure facilities (M = 1.65, S.D = 0.23), support facilities (M = 2.25, SD = 0.18).

Discussion

The discussion summarizes the main findings of the study and relates them to previous research and broader implications. The aim of this research was to assess the school performance, under the Public-Private Partnership (PPP) program, of privatized-public schools compared to low-performing public schools. The results provide important insights regarding educational equity, inclusiveness, and gender parity, leading to a better understanding of why these two types of schools perform differently when compared with each other (Cherchye et al., 2010).

The mean scores of each group on educational equity were also not statistically different from each other (M = 2.74, SD = 0.39 for privatized-public schools, M = 2.72, SD = 0.36 for low-performing public schools; $p = 0.342$), suggesting inclusiveness is prevalent within both institution types. However, the t-test results indicate no significant difference between the two groups ($t=0.169, t = 0.169, p < 0.001, p < 0.001, p < 0.001$), suggesting comparable performance on inclusiveness. These results confirm previous studies on PPPs, where the focus is bringing cost-effective education solutions to the most disadvantaged while maintaining a minimum level of inclusiveness.

Gender parity: diametrically opposed trends in privatized-public schools and poor public schools The privatized-public schools have a gender parity index (1.17), at least that again indicates a tendency to bias toward female students, and reflects the role in promoting women empowerment, through education. In contrast, poorly performing public schools have a gender parity index of 0.88, favoring males. These findings point to a space that seems to address a gender gap more directly than their public counterparts through privatized experiences, corroborating global findings that suggest that PPP schools are much more successful at achieving gender equality through educational experiences.

Although privatized-public and low-performing public schools achieved statistically significant mean scores in different measures of educational equity, such as teacher qualifications, quality of assessment, and physical infrastructure, on some measures such as teacher training workshops and support facilities, the means were slightly lower for the privatized-public schools compared to the low-performing public schools. Such a contrast to the findings of Dr. Momina Afridi in her study, which highlighted deficiencies in PPP schools owing to either lack of investment in teacher training or infrastructure. However, the current research draws on qualitative data from parental interviews, which show that overall satisfaction with PPP schools is high and these perceived deficiencies may not play a key role in shaping parental perceptions of school quality (Nagpal et al., 2021).

Qualitative study of the quality of education in PPP, in collaboration with the World Bank, echoes the same point that there are challenges in maintaining the quality of education with limited resources. These results are in accordance with current literature however current literature uses a mixed-methods approach and this study provides a more thorough analysis. In contrast to Afridi's study, this research includes data from both quantitative instruments and qualitative interviews, providing a much wider view of stakeholder perspectives. Combining these sources of information led to consensus on a higher level of satisfaction with privatized-public schools as these are believed to be more inclusive and gender-parity oriented than bricks-mortar institutions, but one must be cautious regarding teacher-training issues and infrastructural challenges.

The results indicate that privatized-public and low-performing public schools are comparably inclusive by both gender and SES (socioeconomic status); however, privatized-public schools are superior in promoting gender parity. This indicates how PPP programs can help improve women's empowerment and educational equity in Pakistan. But the continued investment in teacher training, physical infrastructure, and other support services will be crucial to maintaining and improving the quality of education in PPP schools.

The study highlights that we need to assess educational equity through a variety of metrics from inclusiveness and gender equity to teacher quality and physical infrastructure. Privatized-public schools demonstrate promise and progress in addressing gender disparities but fall flat in other aspects of education equity compared to other low-performing public schools. Policies from this point on should focus on strengthening teacher preparation and infrastructure to increase educational outcomes in both types of schools and ensure equitable, high-quality education.

Conclusion

The current study revealed that education equity and inclusiveness levels were high in privatized-public schools participating in the Public-Private Partnership (PPP) program and also low-performing public schools. Privatized-public schools exhibited a positively skewed gender parity index (1.17), indicating the role of these schools as enabling institutions for women's empowerment. In contrast, in low-performing public schools, the gender parity index was 0.88 in favor of male students. Although the difference in inclusiveness between these two types of schools was statistically insignificant, privatized-public schools outperformed their peers in gender equity. In addition, privatized-public schools outperformed their counterparts in teacher qualifications, assessment quality, and infrastructure; conversely, low-performing public schools outperformed privatized-public schools in teacher training workshops and support facilities. Questions included parent satisfaction (teachers, parents, and school directors), level of inclusiveness (number of students from the surrounding community), and gender equity (ratio of boys to girls).

Overall, during the interviews, it seemed that parents were, to a large extent, satisfied with the privatized-public schools and reported that they were more inclusive and showed greater gender equity; however, these perceptions were balanced by concerns about the quality of teacher training and the lack of infrastructure that still faced these schools. Overall, the study emphasizes that while co-education can contribute to creating social equivalence in educational systems and may have some implications for gender equity and quality, gender equality and quality education will not be achieved merely by having co-educational systems; conscious and inclusive measures should be undertaken to improve the quality of training of teachers, infrastructure, and access to quality educational materials.

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